

HISTORY OF EMERGENCE AND FORMATION OF SCIENTIFIC SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN PSYCHOLOGY

¹Karshiyeva Yanglish, ²Ravshanov Sobir

¹1st-year basic doctoral student of Gulistan State University

²2nd-year basic doctoral student of Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8055516>

Abstract. *This article discusses the development of psychology in Uzbekistan, the stages of the establishment of psychological scientific centers, the work of scientists and researchers who contributed to it, and the policy being carried out in our country for the development of science.*

Keywords: *psychology, science, consciousness, research, research, area, history, analysis, views, opinion, reflection, development.*

If we pay attention to the history of the development of psychology as a science in our country, it should be noted that it is being formed only during the last decades. But historically, if you analyze the formation of psychology in the territory of Uzbekistan, it can be seen that it was formed in a unique way in the system of religious and philosophical scientists and views. For example, Manichaeism (founded by Mani) or Mazdakism (founded by Mazdak), which developed in the II-III centuries AD, and others widely propagated ideas such as social relations, social justice, and individuality in their system of religious views. But history tells us that there was no integrated, systematic system of social psychological views at all. It should be noted that the psychological research conducted in Uzbekistan is mainly devoted to family and family relations.

For example, the first social psychological research was conducted by Yaqubov in the late 70s and early 80s, and he studied the socio-psychological factors that ensure the stability of family relations and the compatibility of the social roles of the couple. As a result of the research, it was found that the appropriate interaction of family members in terms of roles is an important condition for family harmony. And family conflicts are mainly due to the fact that modern Uzbek women are busy with social work and the preservation of old traditions in family relations.

One of the important researches on the psychology of family relations is N. Soginov's marriage and family relations typical of the Uzbek family - satisfaction with marriage, motives of marriage, age characteristics of family formation typical of Uzbeks, young Uzbek is a scientific work that systematically studied the causes of psychological conflicts and divorces in families. In this study, scientific data that have never been studied before were collected, according to which the main motive that causes the construction of an Uzbek family is "Having a child" (in the first place), and in the second place "Not to be left behind by the public's words", in the third place, "Fulfilling the wishes of parents and people-relatives" and so on. The information collected by N. Soginov is an important scientific guide for young families, conflict families, and those involved in the education of young people.

In addition, a number of studies on the psychology of large groups have been conducted in recent years. For example, V.M. Karimova's research on the mechanism of changes in social perceptions of Uzbek women (1987), E. Usmanov's study of suicidal (i.e. self-immolation) of Uzbek women)'s research on social-psychological causes of behavior (1993), E. No'monova's study on the characteristics of reproductive institutions in Uzbek families, M. Zokirova's study on the uniqueness of perceptions of men's and women's roles Scientific research dedicated to learning,

M. Toshpolatov's work aimed at studying the specific aspects of social behavior of Uzbek youth in the conditions of the market economy, and others are among these. As a result of these studies, a new ethnopsychological concept will be formed in the near future, and it will contribute to the development of scientific work in our republic.

There are very important research topics for psychologists in Uzbekistan, which include the changes occurring in the psychology of individuals and different social groups in the current conditions of independence, social perceptions of people belonging to different age groups, demographic ethnic professional groups, and social behavior based on them. The foundations of scientific management should be developed. That is, the issues of social psychology of production, psychology of management, psychology of groups, and the influence of mass mental processes are waiting for their solution from Uzbek psychologists, in which the national specific aspects of the region should be developed using advanced scientific achievements.

Psychologists who played a great role in the development of the science of psychology are: B. Ananov, P. P. Blonsky, S. L. Rubinshtein, L. Vygotsky, R. S. Nemov, and others, as well as great scientists in Uzbekistan. They include M.G. Davletshin, E.G. Goziev, M. Vahidov, V.A. Tokareva, R.Z. Gainutdinov, V.M. Karimova, G.B. Shoumarov, R.I. Sunnatova, Z.T. Nishonova and others can be included. The above-mentioned scientists, with their ideas and national ideologies, pay attention to the formation of thinking qualities such as independence and criticality in young people.

Pedagogical Museum and Pedagogical Laboratory, which was established in 1918 in Tashkent and later in Shymkent as the first educational and psychological centers, is a universal educational institution that covers all tasks related to education. The educational methods of this aid were produced, tested here and distributed to other educational institutions of the republic. Such organization of the work made it possible to implement. According to the regulations about the pedagogical laboratory, this place should be the center of pedagogical thought and work.

Therefore, on the one hand, it is necessary to give an opportunity to use the rich experience gathered in the laboratory of every innovation of pedagogical work, and this opportunity should be given directly to schools. In addition to other laboratories and offices, there is also an experimental psychological laboratory in the pedagogical laboratory and the pedagogical museum, where various psychological experiments were carried out. It is stressed that it is necessary and general to take mentally ill and psychologically unbalanced children into their education. To propose the establishment of a whole system of special institutions for the same purpose. Croatia's proposal is noteworthy in several ways. First, this is a complex case, and some psychoneurological disease is not excluded.

1. Disease diagnosis (research level);
2. Treatment of patients (practical medical level);
3. Education and training of patients (level of practical education).

It is planned to implement the first level of a psychological laboratory, the second level of a special treatment institution, and the third level of schools. One of the institutions in Turkestan is the "Uzbek State Scientific Research Institute", the current Kori Niyazi Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences, which was established in 1929. Until now, this institute's pedagogical concepts of teaching create the theory of education in schools and preschool institutions. It is the only center. In the early 1930s, the institute had the following offices:

1. Social hygiene.
2. Economy.
3. Pedagogical to pedalo.
4. Psychological laboratory.

Since the establishment of the institute, the in-depth study of the characteristics and social environment of the local people has been engaged in the creation of lessons taking into account the psychological, social and cultural characteristics of children. The main directions of the institute's activities were as follows: 1. Organization of scientific expeditions; 2. Learning children's character; 3. Training of pedagogical personnel.

The activity of this institute is closely connected with the names of such scientists as Bendrikov, Leventuert, Zavarova, Yusupov, Tokanaev, Debenzov, Mirsharipov, Mukhiddinov. In the 1930s, Alexander Romanovich Luria, one of the scientists who made a great contribution to world psychology, worked at this institute. On the basis of the research conducted within his institute, he later published the work "Ob istoricheskome razvitiye poznavatelnykh protsessov" - "On the historical development of cognitive processes". P. Ivanov is one of the scientists who made a great contribution to the formation of the science of psychology in Uzbekistan. In 1940, he published the first textbook on psychology for students of pedagogical institutes. Later, in 1934, in connection with the transformation of the Samarkand Pedagogical Institute into an Uzbek state university, Ivanov moved with his laboratory to the Nizamiy Tashkent State University. Due to the lack of scientific and pedagogical potential in educational institutions of pedagogy, the first psychology classes were conducted with the help of translators, and later these translators themselves began to give lectures on psychology in Uzbek language.

Aliaskar Usmanov, Takhirikhan Askarkhujaev, Baiburova, Rakhmatova and others were teachers of psychology in the Uzbek language. His short essay on "General pedagogy" published in 1927, "school studies" as a general method of education, "General psychology" in the 1940s and 1950s, "Psychological foundations of education" in the 1960s, psychology in Uzbekistan made a great contribution to the development of science. Sh.A. Boyburova, Usmanov worked directly under his leadership. In 1959, under his leadership, Davletshin, Bekboev, Mo`zaffarov, I.P. The Ivanovs defended candidate dissertations.

1963, the first in psychology in Uzbekistan, Krasnoboev Ilya Berov-ich (1896-1968), head of the Department of Logic and Psychology of the Faculty of Philology of Tashkent State University, defended his doctoral thesis on the topic "Formation of faith and moral concepts in high school students". did Krasnoboev's scientific activity has been related to research in Uzbekistan for 20 years. Members of the department of logic and psychology under his leadership:

Mominova, V.Ya. Maros, A. Abdusattorov, V.I. Sofer, A. Gulyamov, R.V. Gulyamov, A. A. Yerstifirov conducted scientific research on psychology and logic in various facilities.

These studies helped to solve the problems related to public education in Uzbekistan. M.Vokhidov (1927-1989) defended his candidacy in Leningrad in 1955, first worked at the Andijan Pedagogical Institute, then at the Institute of Pedagogical Scientific Research named after Kori Niyazi. In 1966, he was elected head of the psychology department of Tashkent State University. In 1973, according to the order of the Council of Ministers, it was established within the Faculty of History by Zinin, L.I. With the participation of Sofer, M. Mamatov and the help of talented scientists of the center, an educational experimental laboratory was established here.

M.Vokhidov wrote textbooks for educational institutions of preschool pedagogy, for pedagogical institutes, in recent years, the textbook "General psychology" edited by Vokhidov Petrovsky was translated, and at the same time, he became famous for creating a textbook in Uzbek, taking into account national and regional characteristics.

Davletshin Gabdulgalimovich was born in 1923. Head of the Department of Psychology of Tashkent State University, Doctor of Psychology, in 1957 he defended his doctoral dissertation on the topic of the formation of technical interests in students of grades "5" and "7", and in 1971, he defended his doctoral dissertation on the topic of the psychology of technical abilities of students. Since 1968, he has been the head of the department of psychology, under the leadership of M. Davletshin, with the help of his direct advice, defended more than 100 candidacy and doctoral theses in Uzbekistan.

F.S. on general, youth pedagogy, social psychology on various problems in Uzbekistan. Ismailova, D.Z. Zaynobiddinov, Majidov, B. Gagshirov, I. Makhmudov, L.K. Saytov, M.I. Musaeva, V.G. Gorobets, D. D. Sharipov, R.K. Shokhnazarov, J.U. Mavlonov, A. Epgptov, A.V. Majitova, M.I. Sagatov, D, Egamberdieva, G, Abdusamatov, K. Sobirov, A. Sindarov and others have grown up. In addition, 25 cases were defended on various issues. Among them, 7 works on the psychology of speech: (P.P. Zamin, N.N. Nigmatov, A.I. Arjonova, Kh. Ochilova, etc.), 4 works on the psychology of memory: (P.I. Ivanov, M.V. Vokhidov, Kh.M. Gafurova, V.P. Ivayova); attention M.Kh. Rakhmonova; 14 works on education (Goziev, Kodirov, Rasulov, Usmonova, Krasnoboev, Tokareva, etc.);

4 works on labor psychology (Turgunov, Sotiboldiev, Yeliseev, Kholmatov); 3 personal cases (Gofurov, Saidullaev, Shapovolov); 1 work on differential psychodiagnostics (Madmarov); 2 works on legal psychology (Ibragimova, Zapryagaev); 3 works on sports psychology (Gapparov, A. Gainutdinov, R. Gainutdinov); 1 work on neuropsychology (Bobojonova); 3 works on the history of psychology (S. Rakhimov) on social psychology (Karimova, Abdumuminov, Tursunov); and other various departments of psychology, many scientists carried out work and brought the science of psychology to Uzbekistan, that is, the concept of psychology, and opened it up to its fullest.

Currently, the field of psychology is gaining attention in Uzbekistan as well. All our scientists who have matured today are striving to make a great contribution to the advancement of psychology in Uzbekistan to the same level as the psychology of foreign countries. They educate people on the basis of national psychology, that is, in the spirit of nationality, and break psychology into their minds. The current state of psychology in Uzbekistan is more advanced than before.

Because this science is reaching people's minds with the opening of training institutions and centers. In addition, it plays a key role in solving various problems in the fields of psychology. Uzbek psychology, namely B. Kadirov, V. Karimova, M. Vokhidov, M. Davletshin and other scientists have made a great contribution to the development of this science. Currently, the science of psychology is also developing its branches.

In short, the development of the science of psychology has an impact on people's lives, that is, on the way of living.

REFERENCES

1. Ghaziev E.G. General psychology. Tashkent. 2002.1-2 books.
2. Yugay A.H., Mirashirova N.A. "Obshchaya psychology" - Tashkent 2014.
3. Druzhinina V.. "Psychology". Textbook. "Peter", 2003.
4. Psychology of the 21st century: theory, practice, perspectives: Proceedings of the international scientific-practical conference, May 22, 2013. Tashkent: MUMTOZ SOZ, 2013
5. Abramova M. Practical psychology M.: Mysl. 2003. - 480 p.